

THE IMPACT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION ON BUSINESS AND THE BUSINESS ENVIRONMENT IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: The article examines how digital economy technologies are changing people's living conditions and economic behavior. The focus is on business behavior and new business environment opportunities. In particular, changes in business strategy, competition, new marketing and customer service opportunities, the emergence of new sources of profit and competitiveness factors are being analyzed. Organizational forms and new methods of doing business in the conditions of digital transformation and digital economy are analyzed..

Keywords: digital economy, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, customer experience, collaborative innovation, price discrimination, platform method, competitive disruption, digital capital, creative capital.

1. Introduction

The technological basis of the digital economy is being created on the basis of the discoveries of the Fourth industrial Revolution. Among them are artificial intelligence, distributed data, the Internet of things and for things, blockchain, mining centers, big data and cloud storage, digital platforms, 3D and then 4D printing. The technological design of various systems is used to solve specific tasks.

After the Fourth Industrial Revolution, there was a shift from the simple dissemination of information technology to a more complex innovation based on the combination of various technologies in new ways. As a result, companies are changing the forms and methods of business, getting the opportunity to create value in new market segments or to find new centers of value creation in their

former industries. Thus, competitive disruption from both the demand side and the supply side forces companies to constantly be innovative, i.e. constantly rebuild and change. New sources of profit and factors of competitiveness. In the digital economy, data-enhanced products become such. A business can have a big impact on the quality of the product, increasing its value and the quality of service by applying digital improvements to its products. By receiving complete information about the operating mode and wear, the business can monitor the continuous improvement of quality without replacing the goods. Technological innovations are transforming the perception and asset management of companies. For example, remote software updates and connectivity increase the value of an already used car instead of its depreciation depreciation. The point is that not only new materials, but also digital processing of data on the operation and condition of the product prolong its high-quality use. This is very important not only for automotive, but also for aviation equipment. Constant monitoring of benchmarks using sensors and algorithms helps to anticipate and eliminate the causes of failures and breakdowns in advance. Thus, maintenance acquires a new quality, special monitoring centers begin to deal with it. On the basis of remote forecasting of the functioning of products, not only remote monitoring centers are created, but also new business models. For example, outsourcing of production facilities that are not strategically significant or specialized. In them, the company can extend the period of uninterrupted operation of machinery and equipment, the functionality of which is determined using analytics.

Thus, digital capital becomes a new source of profit and a factor of business competitiveness. Researchers of the digital and information economy observe a "deepening of capital" and an increase in its contribution to the creation of a new

product relative to the share of labor, which is confirmed by statistical data [5, pp. 33-34]. An important factor in the development and competitiveness of companies working with information and communication technologies is the creativity of employees. In the conditions of digital transformation and the digital economy, it is no longer enough to improve human capital to make super profits. An important factor is the formation of creative capital [6, p. 29], the possession of which brings a stream of superprofits in the implementation of creative ideas. New forms of business. A new form of business cooperation in the digital economy is collaborative innovation. Its emergence is associated with the rapid emergence of innovations and their disruptive impact. Let's say one company lacks capital, knowledge of the intricacies of business and customer base in a particular area. An experienced company has all this, but it lacks digital skills in working with clients and responsive response to changes in their requests. Then enterprises pool their resources, jointly implementing innovative projects. The integration of opportunities contributes to the creation of new value. A striking example is the cooperation of the industrial giant Siemens, which annually invests four billion US dollars in research and development, and the young innovative company Ayasdi. The profile of the latter is self-learning machines, the company was established in Stanford in 2008. As a result, Siemen got the opportunity to generate ideas based on big data processing, and Ayasdi - to test them in practice and at the same time be present on the market using the capabilities of a venerable partner. The derivatives of such cooperation are new forms of business based on shared use, shared storage, etc. For example, associations for the joint use of city vehicles. Enterprises from various industries are brought together for joint customer service (integrated service). Such associations integrate the world of the office and the

world of online business through multilateral cooperation. To make a profit from the use of digital technologies, companies have to radically change their operating models and be very mobile. A new operating model that practices sharing is the platform. The platform method began to be used during the third Industrial Revolution. It is based on the network effect during the transition to the digital space. With the beginning of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, global platforms appeared, closely connected with the physical world. Platform strategies are both disruptive and cost-effective. Research by the University of Massachusetts has shown that out of 30 global brands with the highest total market value, 14 of the largest used platform strategies [11, p. 73]. A good example of a combination of a platform and a highly customer-oriented marketing strategy is Amazon, which has turned from a bookstore into a retail conglomerate, generating \$100 billion in profit annually. The company actively uses network effects, providing access to millions of different books and music through digital stores. A deep understanding of customer preferences and the achievement of high customer loyalty allows you to work simultaneously in several sectors. In revenue generation, the focus shifts from selling a product to selling a service using it and accessing consumers on an almost global scale. The digital platform unites not only producers, but also consumers for sharing. By connecting to a car sharing company, for example, a customer receives mobility services without buying the product itself, and very differentiated by the type of car, price and other individual requests. This service is provided regardless of the location of the client, that is, in any country and city where the network is distributed. Moreover, the corporation providing the sharing service is also not the owner of a car or other good, for example, an apartment, an office, etc. The use of the platform method with deep knowledge of client requests

makes the market transparent and more stable. However, even here there are problems that can be attributed to: a) ownership issues; b) selection from an unlimited supply; c) interaction with platforms that are growing in capacity and provide the widest scale of services. Business environment in the digital community. A new business organizational structure is developing in the digital economy – the blockchain system. Its strong point is decentralization, thanks to which payments move in the global space instantly and transparently. Therefore, there is no need to open many offices and create legal entities with all the administrative costs inherent in them. Blockchain allows you to build a cheap business structure with a small number of internal specialists. The rest may be tens of thousands, dispersed around the world. For example, the global agency IMG has 60 employees and a few people selling advertising. Only one person is responsible for Russia, and that's enough [2]. The principle of global decentralization accelerates the erasure of borders between countries, and with the spread of blockchain, the emergence of a large number of multinational companies is predicted. This is the new organizational structure of business inherent in the digital economy. In the latter, the business environment is changing largely thanks to the blockchain, going into digital codes and cloud computing. In addition to replacing the functions of banks and traditional financial organizations, freeing projects from being tied to the refinancing rate, blockchain in the future will be able to replace courts, lawyers, implementing labor law instead of contracts. A smart contract is a formula "if A, then B" and can be a coded employment contract, according to which, if the specified conditions are met (for example, the variable "dismissal" is less than one), the employee is automatically paid wages and an entry is made in the public register. Cloud organizations and cloud courts also

carry new qualitative characteristics of the business environment becoming digital. For example, the Aragon project creates companies that are everywhere and at the same time nowhere. In other words, a decentralized global company exists outside the country jurisdiction. For business, this is a big saving on intra-company transactions, but for the state it is a problem with taxation and regulation. However, the legal regulation is carried out by the blockchain itself. The smart contract is the guardian of order. In addition, the existence of cloud arbitration is possible: the program itself selects jurors from the blockchain community. They study the documentation and the content of the conflict. The blocked disputed amount, depending on the verdict, either remains on the company's account or is transferred to the employee's account. Thus, moving into the digital space, many institutions, including courts, are changing their organizational form. Problems are resolved quickly and at a high expert level. The electronic code is not subject to bribery or lobbying. The regime of property rights becomes transparent and guaranteed, all other things being equal. Specialists are improving protection against cybercrime. However, this task is now facing the States of the whole world and must be solved at the global level. Blockchain will also help in this area. So, the business environment will be improved when companies switch to digital business technologies and connect them with production. Their use and distribution facilitates the work, primarily reducing transaction costs. This means that additional sources of profit and competitive advantages are being created.

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